

The Queen of Procrastination by Brian Paul Kaess

Hello, (in email to Garret Kaess)

Today, Mayte was running late, and we were late by a few minutes to our appointment at the Diabetic Clinic in Durango City. So Mayte had us rescheduled for October 10. This is the third time we have been late or absent because of Mayte's procrastination, and hopefully we won't 'fall off the grid,' so to speak, as a result. They might have the option to ban us from the clinic, but since they rescheduled- who knows? Maybe we still have a chance, or else, we go somewhere else. Maybe something good can come from this snafu.

We also stopped by Ley Express and Al Super, the former in South Durango City, as well as two other places. Mayte handed me a snack. Mayte likes to procrastinate alot- about my medical appointments, pay days, even my afternoon meals. She still hasn't paid me the money she owes me off of my paycheck. Bitches are tall swindlers! Furthermore, she hasn't helped me apply for a Mexican permanent residence card, which I could surely use. Every time I ask her, she puts it off. Also, she approves all the items I buy at the supermarket, and has even been known to put items of mine back, without my consent. In any case, I guess you gotta stick with the gal you married.

At least when I got home, I was able to feed Nieve some hot, roasted chicken. When she eats- we're such a pair- my stomach feels happy too!

I notice my whole time down here in Mexico, I have never used illicit drugs. In my whole life, I have never asked for illicit drugs, never sold illicit drugs to anyone, or brought illicit drugs to their residence. So, three cheers for some *wholesome* lifestyle choices! I am happy I never took cocaine, like some people in my network.

So, we see that not everything from the city is bad, as some stereotypes might suggest. This is also evidenced by the fact that Mayte and I found love in the city.

We'll see if I can still get the prescribed meds I need as a legitimate diabetic patient. I also heard, with proper treatment, both MS (like Nick) and diabetes patients (like myself) can live a long time, even outside the nursing home regime. So, I hope both Nick and I can make it.

Brian